

Research Article

Ancient Period in Medical Ethical Perspectives

Eswararao Vanka

* Research Scholar, Department of Philosophy, Andhra University, Visakhapatnam

Corresponding Author: Eswararao Vanka, Email id: eswararao1225@gmail.com

Abstract

Medical ethics is an applied branch of ethics or moral philosophy. It attempts to unravel the rights and wrongs of different areas of health care practice in the light of philosophical analysis. The study focus on the medical ethics in ancient period in philosophical views of ayurveda.

Keywords: Medical Ethics, Ancient Period, Ayurveda.

Ancient Indian thoughts, philosophy a developed with a rational synthesis an gathering into itself new concepts. Spiritual was the foundation of India's cultural his to spirituality, dharnza (ethical conduct according state) was the most important concept of India Both are unfortunately, on the decline.

India has been blessed with a glorious code on medical ethics since the days of Caraka and Susruta (circa 600 BC). This Ayurvedic code embodies the criteria for a good teacher and who should study medicine, It also offers counsel on behaviour with patients and their relatives and pointers that can be used by us when dealing with such issues as brain death and organ transplantation

Ayurveda is considered by many scholars to be the oldest healing science. In Sanskrit, Ayurveda means "The Science of Life." Ayurvedic knowledge originated in India more than 5,000 years ago and is often called the "Mother of All Healing." It stems from the ancient Vedic culture and was taught for many thousands of years in an oral tradition from accomplished masters to their disciples. Some of this knowledge was set to print a few thousand years ago, but much of it is inaccessible. The principles of many of the natural healing systems now familiar in the West have their roots in Ayurveda, including Homeopathy and Polarity Therapy.

Ayurveda places great emphasis on prevention and encourages the maintenance of health through close attention to balance in one's life, right thinking, diet, lifestyle and the use of herbs. Knowledge of Ayurveda enables one to understand how to create this balance of body, mind and consciousness according to one's own individual constitution and how to make lifestyle changes to bring about and maintain this balance.

Just as everyone has a unique fingerprint, each person has a particular pattern of energy—an individual combination of physical, mental and emotional characteristics—which comprises

their own constitution. This constitution is determined at conception by a number of factors and remains the same throughout one's life.

Many factors, both internal and external, act upon us to disturb this balance and are reflected as a change in one's constitution from the balanced state. Examples of these emotional and physical stresses include one's emotional state, diet and food choices, seasons and weather, physical trauma, work and family relationships. Once these factors are understood, one can take appropriate actions to nullify or minimize their effects or eliminate the causes of imbalance and re-establish one's original constitution. Balance is the natural order; imbalance is disorder. Health is order; disease is disorder. Within the body there is a constant interaction between order and disorder. When one understands the nature and structure of disorder, one can re-establish order.

Vata, Pitta and Kapha: Balancing the Three Principle Energies of the Body

Ayurveda identifies three basic types of energy or functional principles that are present in everyone and everything. Since there are no single words in English that convey these concepts, we use the original Sanskrit words vata, pitta and kapha. These principles can be related to the basic biology of the body.

Energy is required to create movement so that fluids and nutrients get to the cells, enabling the body to function. Energy is also required to metabolize the nutrients in the cells, and is called for to lubricate and maintain the structure of the cell. Vata is the energy of movement; pitta is the energy of digestion or metabolism and kapha, the energy of lubrication and structure. All people have the qualities of vata, pitta and kapha, but one is usually primary, one secondary and the third is usually least prominent. The cause of disease in Ayurveda is viewed as a lack of proper cellular function due to an excess or deficiency of vata, pitta or kapha. Disease can also be caused by the presence of toxins.

In Ayurveda, body, mind and consciousness work together in maintaining balance. They are simply viewed as different facets of one's being. To learn how to balance the body, mind and consciousness requires an understanding of how vata, pitta and kapha work together. According to Ayurvedic philosophy the entire cosmos is an interplay of the energies of the five great elements—Space, Air, Fire, Water and Earth. Vata, pitta and kapha are combinations and permutations of these five elements that manifest as patterns present in all creation. In the physical body, vata is the subtle energy of movement, pitta the energy of digestion and metabolism, and kapha the energy that forms the body's structure.

Vata is the subtle energy associated with movement — composed of Space and Air. It governs breathing, blinking, muscle and tissue movement, pulsation of the heart, and all movements in the cytoplasm and cell membranes. In balance, vata promotes creativity and flexibility. Out of balance, vata produces fear and anxiety.

Pitta expresses as the body's metabolic system — made up of Fire and Water. It governs digestion, absorption, assimilation, nutrition, metabolism and body temperature. In balance, pitta promotes understanding and intelligence. Out of balance, pitta arouses anger, hatred and jealousy.

Kapha is the energy that forms the body's structure — bones, muscles, tendons — and provides the "glue" that holds the cells together, formed from Earth and Water. Kapha supplies

the water for all bodily parts and systems. It lubricates joints, moisturizes the skin, and maintains immunity. In balance, kapha is expressed as love, calmness and forgiveness. Out of balance, it leads to attachment, greed and envy.

Life presents us with many challenges and opportunities. Although there is much over which we have little control, we do have the power to decide about some things, such as diet and lifestyle. To maintain balance and health, it is important to pay attention to these decisions. Diet and lifestyle appropriate to one's individual constitution strengthen the body, mind and consciousness.

Suśruta says that Āyur-veda (the science of life) is an upāṅga of the Atharva-Veda and originally consisted of 100,000 verses in one thousand chapters and was composed by Brahmā before he created all beings (Suśruta-saṁhitā, 1. 1. 5). What upāṅga exactly means in this connection cannot easily be satisfactorily explained. Dalhaṇa (A.D. 1100) in explaining the word in his Nibandha-saṁgraha, says that an upāṅga is a smaller aṅga (part)- "aṅgam eva alpatvād upāṅgam." Thus, while hands and legs are regarded as aṅgas, the toes or the palms of the hands are called upāṅga.

Ayurveda fundamentals

Ayurveda has various fundamental theories like Panchamahabhuta, Purusha, Loka concept, Guna, Dosha, Dhatu, Mala, Srotasa, Agni, Manas etc. Ayurveda fundamental concepts were derived from:

1. Philosophies and knowledge base available during the contemporary period like Darshanas
2. Experimental testing through practical or clinical testing. Analyzing the results and cyclically applying them to the fundamental concepts
3. Keen observation of the natural phenomenon. Trying to understand the details and making fundamental concepts
4. Making a macroscopic view of the systems, body, environment, and natural sciences
5. The traditional experimental approach was different from the current scientific approach, like the use of Pramanas, Tantra Yukti, Siddhanta, etc. Current science also uses evidence, theory, logic, etc. Fundamentals of these can be seen in both approaches but differ in methodology.

Many Western biomedical explanatory models of the body are from the biochemistry basis than physics. Concepts in Traditional systems of medicine are nearer to physics than to chemistry. Emerging studies from biophysics can be of use in understanding them. A study has shown that water and living bodies have macroscopic coherent properties of quantum mechanical origin. These contribute to the understanding of physics associated with homeopathy, acupuncture, etc.

This medical system was well established around 2500 to 600 B.C, when it evolved into 2 schools, The school of physicians and the school of surgeons, similar to allopathy, charaka samhita, susrut samhita, and Ashtang Hridaya samhita are the senior triad texts and Madhav Nidan Samhita, Sarangdha samhita, and Bhavaparakash samhita are the junior triad texts, around 600 B.C , Ayurveda was branched into internal medicine; pediatrics; psychiatry, surgery, eye, ear, nose and throat, toxicology, geriatrics, and eugenics or aphrodisiacs. The body is composed of 3 body doshas, 3 mental doshas, 7 dhatus, and malas.

References:

1. Bodeker G. Evaluating Ayurveda J Altern Complement Med. 2001;7:389-92
2. Smith CW. Quanta and coherence effects in water and living systems J Altern Complement Med. 2004;10:69-78
3. Surendranath Dasgupta, "A history of Indian Philosophy" volume II ;Delhi ,1988,1991: Motilal banarsidass

Citation: Eswararao Vanka, 2024. "Ancient Period in Medical Ethical Perspectives". International Journal of Academic Research, 11(2): 75-78.

Copyright: ©2024 Eswararao Vanka, This is an open-access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.